

SMILE AND ITS RELATIONSHIP WITH MOOD

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Whereas, since a person has created a calm external environment around himself, sometimes he must have established calmness within himself as well. If the mind is prepared to think, but the attention is divided, the goals are confused, the plan is not formed, then the person cannot achieve the inner smile.

A relaxed state of mind and thirty-six deep breaths with the belly help to calm the mind and begin to relax the body. But achieving a state of complete relaxation means something greater than simply relaxing tense muscles and agitated nerves. Achieving a deep and lasting state of relaxation. requires creating a sense of calmness in the internal organs. A clear sky and a calm sea around the soul, only all the internal organs, the heart, lungs, liver, the kidneys, the stomach, as well as the nervous system and the circulatory system, feel themselves only when they feel relaxed. Smile has healing power. For example, when a person is on the street, overwhelmed by everything, worried about things to do, relationships with other people, about work, about his whole life, when suddenly some passing person smiles, the depressed person does not even realize it. also smiles at him. At some point in the moment, he lets go of his unconsciousness and keeps walking, knowing that everything will be fine. So, a sincere smile is a huge has power.

A smile can be considered as a facial expression of an upbeat state. So. It is important to be in a good mood to smile. What should you pay attention to in order to be in a good mood? Questions lead to the first destination. The first

destination is the mood.

Even if the concept of mood is approached from different points of view in psychological sources, they mean the same in content. For example, in the dictionary of K. Turgunov, a relatively stable general emotional state of a person with weak or moderate strength, in the textbook "General Psychology" of A. V. Petrovsky, moods express the general emotional state that affects the entire behavior of a person for a long time. , it is noted.

According to Professor E. Ghaziyev, mood is an emotional state that affects the mental processes of a person for a certain period of time.[1; 249.] Mood, that is, a person's happy or sad mood, never appears without a reason. A successful completion of a task or an exam is good the transition brings about a good refreshing mood. The fact that your work does not go forward or a bad evaluation gives a person a feeling of depression and lack of confidence in his strength. Good or bad mood is primarily related to a person's health. For example, when we have a severe stomach ache, we are not in a good mood.

Usually, a person may have one or another type of mood, that is, cheerfulness, happiness or sadness, sadness, depression. According to this, people are divided into different groups: happy, sad, nervous. But it should be said that a person should not be a slave to his mood, but should be able to control it. People who can control their moods are always in good spirits, high spirits and productive at work. People who can't control their moods have a hard time living in life. Such people are the ones who get upset over trifles or get upset. Such a person is usually called "a person whose vinegar does not hold water" or "a person who keeps his nose on the tip of his anger." If a person always thinks and acts wisely, he will not be disturbed by things that did not happen.[2;250]

It is necessary to analyze the following two factors that influence the emergence and change of human mood: One of them is an objective and subjective situation: a) a situation related to natural factors (coldness or heat of the

air); b) inconvenience of interpersonal relations, etc. The latter can be interpreted as a source, which is subjective, conditions. For example, the availability of necessary tools for work and study activities. The second is subjective relations, a warm psychological environment, a ritual of sociability. encouragement, communication style, privacy, equal rights, consideration of psychological characteristics of a person, etc.

An event that happened in a person's personal or social life and is of great importance to this person can be the reason for the birth of this kind of mood. The successful completion of a task can cause a person to feel joy and happiness that lasts for several days. A high rating given by an authoritative person or an institution for the successful completion of a job makes a person happy. Trouble at work, failure, low evaluation of a person's work lowers his spirit, causes disappointment in him, creates distrust in his own strength. [3;230]

The state of the nervous system in a person and the state of a person's health in general can cause a certain mood to arise in a person. Sometimes a person does not understand the reason that caused a certain mood in him. Such a phenomenon often occurs due to the state of the body, including the state of the nervous system. Usually, one or another mood can prevail in a certain person. Usually, depending on what kind of mood prevails, we call some people happy, cheerful, cheerful people, and some people we call sad, depressed, careless people. Such a prevailing mood becomes a characteristic of a person's character. Mood plays a major role in all mental processes and activities of a person. Mood affects the rate at which ideas and thoughts flow, as well as the content and direction of ideas and thoughts. Mood to all other emotional experiences in a person. usually exerts its influence, this change of mood in the activity of aspirations, aspirations and actions shows. When a person smiles at someone, they feel better. When you smile at plants, they feel your human love energy and grow better. If a person yells at their loved ones, they feel humiliated and unhappy.

A sincere smile is a sign of love and energy that has a warming and healing effect is a transmitter. It's like a tool for making music. The one who doesn't smile a person is like a guitar that is not being played: the guitar is standing in the corner, it starts to shrivel, its strings are pulled and gradually it breaks and decays. Similarly, a person who does not smile cannot develop his ability to love and smile. His sullen facial expression and overly serious approach to life often cause cancer and stomach ailments. As a result, his life begins to slowly decay due to the lack of love. A smiling person brings joy to people's lives and even after physical death people live happy and healthy lives that they can remember for a very long time. A person cannot know the power of a smile and appreciate all its potential until he understands the difference between happiness and people, and is still able to associate happiness with health and sadness with illness. In short, its internal

does not seriously feel the problem of a smile aimed at his organs and nervous system. At this point, a hadith about smiling is quoted. Our Prophet (pbuh) said, "A smile is also charity." That is, it is said that "a person who smiles gets the reward of a person who gives charity." A smiling person can have a positive effect on himself and others. Smiling to yourself guarantees happiness, health and longevity.

References:

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